

A continuum damage mechanics model for short fiber reinforced composites

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Introduction

short fiber reinforced composites

- lightweight materials
- high flexibility regarding design of component shape and complexity
- easy processing using injection molding
- popular materials in many automotive and other transport applications

fatigue under in-service conditions complex process depending on

- fiber volume fraction
 - fiber orientation distribution
 - local loading situation – triaxial stress state
- advanced material model accounting for all relevant effects required for numerical simulation

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Experimental study

fatigue crack formation and propagation

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Experimental study

fatigue of notched specimens

- S-N-curves based on crack initiation shifted with respect to S-N-curves based on specimen failure
- creep affects slope of S-N-curves
- investigated further in tests at variable temperature

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Fatigue degradation model

damage variable

- starting point: orthotropic three-dimensional linear elasticity
- introduction of damage

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{33} \\ 2\varepsilon_{23} \\ 2\varepsilon_{13} \\ 2\varepsilon_{12} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{(1-D)E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{(1-D)E_2} & -\frac{\nu_{32}}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{13}}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2} & \frac{1}{(1-D)E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-D)G_{23}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-D)G_{13}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-D)G_{12}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{pmatrix}$$

- single damage variable: $D = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{initial, undamaged state} \\ 0, \dots, 1 & \text{partially damaged state} \\ 1 & \text{material failure} \end{cases}$

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Fatigue degradation model

damage initiation

- failure envelope
 - elastic domain assumed to be bounded by a Tsai-Wu-type failure envelope
 - damage activation function similar to Maimí et al.'s approach:

$$F = \phi - 1 \leq 0$$

- stress function in 3D-strain space:

$$\phi = \left(\left(\frac{\varepsilon_{11}}{\gamma_{11}^t} \right)^2 - \frac{\varepsilon_{11} \varepsilon_{22}}{\gamma_{1122}^t} + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{22}}{\gamma_{22}^t} \right)^2 - \frac{\varepsilon_{22} \varepsilon_{33}}{\gamma_{2233}^t} + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{33}}{\gamma_{33}^t} \right)^2 - \frac{\varepsilon_{33} \varepsilon_{11}}{\gamma_{1133}^t} + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{23}}{\gamma_{23}^s} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{13}}{\gamma_{13}^s} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{12}}{\gamma_{12}^s} \right)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

- critical strains $\gamma_{ij}, \gamma_{klpq}$: material strength parameters to be determined experimentally
- static failure once actual strain state reaches failure envelope

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Fatigue degradation model

damage evolution

- previous 1D stress based model:

- damage driven by microplastic work: $dD \sim dw$
- microplastic work increment estimated from Ramberg-Osgood equation

- resulting in:
$$dD \begin{cases} \sim \sigma^n d\sigma & \text{if } \sigma \geq 0 \\ = 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

- assumption here: damage driven by approach of the failure envelope by actual strain state

$$dD = \begin{cases} A \phi^n d\phi & \text{if } d\phi \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad \text{with } A = 1 + n \quad \text{due to } \int_{\phi=0}^1 dD = 1$$

- material parameters: $\gamma_{11}^t, \gamma_{1122}^t, \gamma_{22}^t, \gamma_{2233}^t, \gamma_{33}^t, \gamma_{1133}^t, \gamma_{23}^s, \gamma_{13}^s, \gamma_{12}^s, n$

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Fatigue degradation model

effect of fiber orientation distribution

- definition of the fiber orientation in terms of the second order fiber orientation tensor

$$a_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{13} & a_{23} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix} \text{ or alternatively in principal axes space } a_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} a_I & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{II} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a_{III} \end{pmatrix}$$

- determination of the parameters in the principal axes system at three reference states
- interpolation in between the orientation states
- for variable temperature interpolation between selected discrete “thermal nodes”

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Implementation and validation

implementation as a user defined model into commercial finite element program (ABAQUS)

- time domain formulation
- numerically efficient formulation since strain space formulation avoids (iterative) solution of local nonlinear system of equations

preliminary validation against experimental data base at coupon level

- material PA66 GF35
- tension-tension fatigue ($R=0.1$) at 10 Hz
- specimen orientation: 0° , 30° , 90°
- ambient temperature (23°C)
- dry as molded condition (rel. humidity < 0.1 wt%)

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Simplified post-processing routine

post-processing version of the model implemented in Python 3:

- neglects creep → linear model → unit-load FEA and scaling of strain results

$$\varepsilon_{ij,ref} = f(L_{ref}) \quad \varepsilon_{ij}(t) = \frac{L(t)}{L_{ref}} \varepsilon_{ij,ref} \quad i, j \in \{1,2,3\}$$

- numerical integration of damage evolution for nodal strain-time function

$$D = \int \frac{dD}{dt} dt = \int A \Phi^n \frac{d\Phi}{dt} dt \quad \text{for } d\Phi > 0$$

with A , Φ , n defined as above.

- lower computational expenses but simplification reduces accuracy

contour plot of nodal fatigue lives (example)
source: final report IGF-project no. 20474 N

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Examples

preliminary validation against experimental data base at coupon level

■ results

- good approximation of experimental results by proposed fatigue damage model
- perfect prediction of S-N-curve as straight line in double logarithmic representation

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Examples

validation under bending and variable temperature: "T"-specimens

- geometry and loading conditions

- results

- good approximation of lifetime by proposed model

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Examples

validation under multi axial loading: "submarine"-specimen"

- geometry and loading conditions

- divided into two internal chambers (interconnected)
- loaded by cyclic internal pressure at ambient temperature

block no.	no. of load cycles	relative amplitude
1	166	0.749164612677923
2	11	0.894628660359632
3	37380	0.235698727762764
4	645	0.660797070405397
5	4	1.000000000000000
6	2495	0.558028733780214
7	43	0.827064354881646
8	9656	0.430947432193174

- results

- correct prediction of failure spot
- satisfactory prediction of S-N-curve

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Conclusions

continuum damage model for short fiber composites

- linear elasticity model with anisotropic damage
- strain space defined damage formulation based on single damage variable
- relevant damage mechanisms: pore formation and growth

implementation and validation

- time domain formulation
- user-defined subroutine into commercial FE code
- almost perfect agreement at coupon level
- satisfactory results under more complex loading conditions

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